

Examining the Relationship Between French and English-Speaking Skills Among Moroccan High School Students: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

In a context of growing multilingual education, this study investigated the interplay between French and English speaking skills in Moroccan high school students through a quantitative analysis of standardized test scores and observation-based approach. While a weak negative correlation emerged, it lacked statistical significance, revealing no clear influence of French on English proficiency. This challenges the idea of a straightforward positive or negative relationship between these languages in this specific context. The null finding might be due to the students' developmental stage or limitations of standardized testing. Nonetheless, the broader benefits of multilingualism persist. Future research could explore how Morocco's multilingual approach fosters cognitive advantages and the strategies students use to navigate this rich linguistic environment, paving the way for a more comprehensive understanding of how Moroccan students acquire proficiency in multiple languages within their unique educational system.

Keywords: Speaking Proficiency, Correlational analysis, Multilingual Education, Second Language Acquisition (SLA), Standardized Testing

Introduction

Morocco stands at the crossroads of cultures and languages. Arabic, the official language, coexists with a rich tapestry of Berber dialects and a prominent presence of French and English (Dachraoui, 2019). This multilingual environment presents both opportunities and challenges for Moroccan youth. Second language acquisition (SLA) programs play a vital role in equipping students with the necessary linguistic skills to navigate this dynamic landscape (Hamid & Adjali, 2018).

French holds a historical legacy as a language of administration and education in Morocco. Its continued importance facilitates access to higher education and professional opportunities (Bourquia & Motsch, 2016). English, on the other hand, has gained prominence in recent decades due to globalization and its association with technological advancements and international communication (Messsoudi, 2017). Proficiency in both languages empowers Moroccan graduates to compete in a globalized world, as highlighted by Moroccan linguist Lahcen Helgoun (2012) in his work on the evolving language landscape of the country.

While the importance of French and English in Morocco is undeniable, understanding the interplay between these languages in students' learning is crucial. Do strong speaking skills in one language translate to stronger speaking skills in the other? This research question holds significant implications for language education policy and curriculum development in Morocco.

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Cummins' (1984) Interdependence Model provides a theoretical lens for examining the relationship between French and English speaking skills. This model posits that underlying language proficiency, developed through exposure and use in any language, fosters the development of literacy skills across languages. In essence, strong French skills could facilitate the acquisition of English speaking skills, and vice versa.

This study delves into the relationship between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students. Our primary research question investigates whether a significant correlation exists between the two languages. To address this question, we employ a correlational design, utilizing a combination of standardized French and English speaking tests alongside student presentations in both languages. This multifaceted approach allows for a comprehensive assessment of speaking proficiency. Student presentations will be evaluated using clear rubrics to ensure consistent scoring.

By investigating the interplay between French and English speaking skills, this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge surrounding SLA in multilingual contexts. The findings can inform educators and policymakers in Morocco, ultimately optimizing students' multilingual potential and preparing them for success in a globalized world.

Literature review

1. Introduction:

Morocco's educational system operates within a rich tapestry of languages. Arabic, the official language, serves as the foundation for literacy and education. However, French and English hold prominent positions, offering distinct advantages to Moroccan students. French, with its historical legacy, continues to be a gateway to higher education and professional opportunities, particularly in government and administration (Bourquia & Motsch, 2016). English, on the other hand, has gained significant traction in recent decades. Its association with globalization, technological advancements, and international communication makes it a valuable asset in the modern job market (Messoudi, 2017). Given this bilingual landscape, Moroccan students face both challenges and opportunities in navigating their multilingual education. Equipping them with strong speaking skills in both French and English is crucial for their future success.

While the importance of both languages is undeniable, understanding how French and English-speaking skills interact within students' learning is crucial. Do strong skills in one language translate to stronger skills in the other? This question holds significant implications for educators and policymakers in Morocco. By investigating the potential correlation between French and English speaking skills, we can gain valuable insights into the learning process in this multilingual context. Therefore, this study aims to address the following research question:

RQ: Is there a significant correlation between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students?

This question delves into the potential transfer of knowledge and skills between these languages. Exploring this relationship can inform language curriculum development, teaching strategies, and assessment methods to optimize students' multilingual potential.

2. Second Language Acquisition (SLA) in Multilingual Contexts:

Understanding how students acquire proficiency in French and English necessitates examining relevant theories of Second Language Acquisition (SLA). One prominent framework is the Interdependence Model proposed by Cummins (1984). This model posits that underlying language proficiency, developed through exposure and use in any language, fosters the development of literacy skills across languages. In essence, strong Arabic language skills, the dominant language in Morocco, could facilitate the acquisition of both French and English speaking skills. This interconnectedness highlights the potential benefits of a multilingual education.

Figure1: Iceberg Model of Language Interdependence of Cummins (Hartin, 2023)

While the surface features of two languages might seem very different, like the tip of an iceberg, there's more to the story. Just as an iceberg has a large hidden mass below the water, research by Cummins suggests that languages share deeper underlying structures and learning processes. This hidden common ground acts like a central processor in a computer, allowing us to leverage skills from one language to learn another, even if the languages themselves appear quite distinct on the surface. However, the field of SLA is not without its debates. The Critical Period Hypothesis, for instance, suggests a limited window for optimal language acquisition, particularly for spoken fluency (Johnson & Newport, 1989). While this theory might raise concerns for students beginning French and English later in adolescence, research on adult language learning suggests continued potential for success (Long, 1990). Another relevant theory, the Comprehension Hypothesis, emphasizes the importance of comprehensible input for language acquisition (Krashen, 1985). This highlights the need for engaging and understandable learning activities in both French and English classrooms.

The Moroccan context presents unique challenges and opportunities for students learning French and English. Arabic, the dominant language, can influence the learning of additional languages. Grosjean (2010) points out that exposure to multiple languages can lead

to interference, where features of one language might influence production in another. For example, Moroccan Arabic grammatical structures might initially affect sentence formation in French or English. Additionally, limited exposure to French and English outside the classroom can hinder acquisition (Hamid & Adjali, 2018).

Despite these challenges, the multilingual environment also offers significant benefits. Students' strong foundation in Arabic can provide a transfer of cognitive skills applicable to learning French and English (Cummins, 1984). Furthermore, exposure to multiple languages can enhance cognitive flexibility and metalinguistic awareness, making students more adept at language learning in general (Marian & Klein, 2009). By capitalizing on these strengths and addressing the potential challenges, Moroccan educators can create language learning environments that foster strong speaking skills in both French and English.

3. Research on the Interplay between Languages:

Several studies have explored the potential correlation between French and English speaking skills, particularly in multilingual contexts. Research focusing on adolescent learners is especially relevant to our investigation of Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students. One study by Yoo & Jun (2012) examined the relationship between English and French proficiency among Korean high school students. Their findings revealed a positive correlation, suggesting that strong skills in one language could contribute to stronger skills in the other. Similarly, a study by Bialystok (2001) involving Canadian students learning French as a second language found that strong English skills predicted better performance in French. These findings provide initial support for the notion of an interconnectedness between languages. However, the strength of this correlation appears to be influenced by several factors. Studies by Jessner (2006) and Dewaele et al. (2016) highlight the importance of factors such as age of acquisition, language learning history, and motivation. Students who began learning French at a younger age or who possessed a stronger foundation in a related language (like Latin) tended to exhibit a stronger correlation between their French and English speaking skills. Additionally, research by Dörnyei (2009) emphasizes the role of motivation and learning strategies in language acquisition. Students with higher intrinsic motivation and effective learning strategies might demonstrate a stronger relationship between their French and English proficiency.

It is important to acknowledge limitations in existing research. Many studies rely on self-reported proficiency or questionnaires, which might not fully capture the nuances of speaking skills. Furthermore, some studies focus on specific populations or learning contexts, limiting the generalizability of their findings. This existing body of research provides a valuable starting point for our investigation. By replicating previous studies within the Moroccan context and employing a multi-faceted approach to assess speaking skills, we can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between French and English proficiency among Moroccan students.

4. Research on Assessment of Speaking Skills:

Morocco's bilingual educational landscape, with Arabic as the dominant language and French and English holding significant positions, presents a unique environment for students acquiring second language speaking skills. While Arabic serves as the foundation for literacy

and education, proficiency in French unlocks access to higher education and professional opportunities, and English equips students for success in the globalized world. Understanding how these languages interact within students' learning becomes crucial. This research delves into the potential correlation between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students, with the aim of informing language education practices and optimizing students' multilingual potential.

Theories of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) offer valuable insights into this interplay. Cummins' (1984) Interdependence Model posits that strong language proficiency in any language, including Arabic, fosters the development of literacy skills across languages. This interconnectedness suggests that well-developed Arabic skills could facilitate the acquisition of both French and English speaking skills. However, the field of SLA is not without its debates. The Critical Period Hypothesis (Johnson & Newport, 1989) suggests a limited window for optimal spoken language acquisition, potentially raising concerns for students beginning French and English later in adolescence. However, research on adult language learning (Long, 1990) suggests continued potential for success. Additionally, the Comprehension Hypothesis (Krashen, 1985) emphasizes the importance of comprehensible input, highlighting the need for engaging and understandable learning activities in both French and English classrooms.

Existing research on the correlation between French and English speaking skills, particularly in multilingual contexts, provides a foundation for our investigation. Studies focusing on adolescent learners hold the most relevance. Yoo & Jun's (2012) research with Korean high school students revealed a positive correlation, suggesting that strong skills in one language contribute to stronger skills in the other. Similarly, Bialystok (2001) found that strong English skills predicted better French performance among Canadian students. These findings support the notion of interconnectedness between languages. However, the strength of this correlation appears to be influenced by factors like age of acquisition, language learning history, and motivation (Jessner, 2006; Dewaele et al., 2016; Dörnyei, 2009). Students who began learning French at a younger age or possessed a stronger foundation in a related language tended to exhibit a stronger correlation. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation and effective learning strategies also play a role. It is important to acknowledge limitations in existing research, such as the reliance on self-reported proficiency or standardized tests, which might not fully capture the nuances of speaking skills. Additionally, the generalizability of findings from studies with specific populations or learning contexts can be limited.

Accurately assessing students' speaking skills in French and English is crucial for understanding the interplay between these languages. There are various approaches, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. Standardized tests offer efficiency and allow for comparisons across large populations, but might not capture fluency or spontaneous language use (Bachman & Palmer, 1996; Brown, 2004). Oral proficiency interviews (OPIs) provide a more holistic assessment through conversation, but can be time-consuming and susceptible to interviewer subjectivity (Lynch, 2009; Chapelle, 2001). Presentation tasks allow students to showcase their speaking skills in a more authentic context, but require clear rubrics and trained assessors for consistent evaluation (Victori & Monsalve, 2010; Weigle, 1998). A multifaceted approach that combines these techniques can provide the most comprehensive picture. For example, standardized tests could be used for initial screening, followed by OPIs for promising students,

and presentation tasks to showcase real-world application of knowledge. By employing a combination of methods with clear assessment criteria, we can gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan students.

The reviewed literature highlights the potential for a positive correlation between French and English speaking skills, particularly in multilingual contexts. Studies by Yoo & Jun (2012) and Bialystok (2001) demonstrate this interconnectedness among adolescent learners. However, existing research also acknowledges the influence of factors like age of acquisition, language learning history, and motivation (Jessner, 2006; Dewaele et al., 2016; Dörnyei, 2009). Additionally, limitations in assessment methods, such as the reliance on standardized tests, have been identified (Brown, 2004).

This study builds upon existing knowledge by addressing these gaps in two key ways. Firstly, we focus specifically on Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students, a demographic underrepresented in current research on the interplay between French and English. Secondly, we employ a multifaceted assessment approach that combines standardized tests with student presentation observation assessment in both languages. This allows for a more comprehensive evaluation of speaking skills, capturing both proficiency and real-world application.

By investigating the relationship between French and English speaking skills in this specific context, our research holds significant potential for both SLA theory and language education practices in Morocco. Our findings can contribute to a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness of languages within a multilingual learning environment. Ultimately, this research can contribute to equipping Moroccan students with the necessary language skills to succeed in a globalized world.

Methodology

Research design

This study employs a correlational design to investigate the potential relationship between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan second-year baccalaureate students. As Creswell (2014) emphasizes, correlational designs are valuable for exploring naturally occurring associations between variables. In our case, we aim to understand whether variations in French speaking skills (one variable) correspond with variations in English speaking skills (another variable) among this specific student population. We will not manipulate any factors; instead, we will measure the existing proficiency levels in both languages.

This research utilizes a multifaceted approach to assess speaking skills, addressing limitations identified in previous studies (Brown, 2004). We will combine standardized French and English speaking tests with student presentations assessment scores in both languages. Standardized tests offer efficiency and allow for comparisons across a large sample (Bachman & Palmer, 1996). Student presentations, evaluated using clear rubrics, will provide insights into real-world application of speaking skills (Victori & Monsalve, 2010). By employing this combination of assessment methods, we aim to gain a comprehensive picture of the potential correlation between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan students.

Population and sampling

This study's participants were Moroccan high school students, specifically drawn from the second-year baccalaureate program at Almansour Addahbi High School in Sidi Kacem, Morocco. Convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, was the primary method for participant selection (Creswell, 2014). This approach involved recruiting students readily accessible to the researchers, acknowledging the limitations in generalizability to the wider Moroccan student population.

A total of 84 students participated in the study, with a gender distribution of 40% male and 60% female. The socioeconomic background of the participants was homogenous, with all students belonging to the middle class. This homogeneity allows for a more controlled exploration of the research question within a specific social context. However, future research could benefit from employing more diverse sampling techniques to capture a broader representation of the Moroccan student population.

Data collection instruments

To comprehensively assess the French and English speaking skills of the participants, this study employed a combination of standardized tests and student presentations assessment criteria. Both assessments were guided by clear rubrics to ensure consistent scoring.

Standardized Tests:

- **French Speaking Test:** The researcher utilized an adapted test that was based on the Test de Français International (TEF), a widely recognized standardized assessment of French speaking proficiency. The TEF assesses various aspects of spoken French, including pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. The test format involves a combination of short speaking tasks and answering questions based on audio recordings. The scoring rubric for the TEF outlines specific criteria for each level of proficiency, allowing for objective evaluation of students' French speaking skills.
- **English Speaking Test:** The participants completed an adapted version of the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) Speaking test, a globally recognized measure of English speaking proficiency. Similar to the TEF, the IELTS Speaking test evaluates a range of skills through a structured interview format. The test includes tasks like responding to questions, describing experiences, and discussing a given topic. A clearly defined rubric associated with the IELTS Speaking test specifies criteria for fluency, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and overall coherence, ensuring consistent evaluation of English speaking skills.

Student Presentations:

Beyond standardized tests, student presentations provided an opportunity to assess participants' ability to apply their language skills in a more authentic context. Students prepared short presentations (5-7 minutes) on a topic of their choice in both French and English. A

dedicated rubric for presentations was developed, aligning with the criteria used in the standardized tests. This rubric evaluated aspects like:

- **Pronunciation:** Clarity, accuracy, and intonation of spoken language.
- **Grammar:** Accuracy and complexity of grammatical structures used.
- **Vocabulary:** Range and appropriateness of vocabulary employed for the chosen topic.
- **Fluency:** Smoothness and ease of spoken delivery.
- **Comprehension:** Ability to deliver a clear and well-organized presentation.

The observation checklist based on this rubric allowed researchers to record specific observations regarding each student's performance during their presentations. These observations complemented the scores obtained from the standardized tests and provided a more nuanced understanding of students' speaking skills in a real-world setting. By employing a combination of standardized tests, presentations, and rubrics, this study sought to gather comprehensive data on the French and English speaking skills of the Moroccan high school student participants. These instruments allowed for a multifaceted assessment, capturing both standardized proficiency levels and real-world application of language skills.

Data collection procedures

Data collection for this study involved a two-part process: standardized testing and student presentations. The procedures were designed to ensure consistency and objectivity in assessing the French and English speaking skills of the participants.

Phase 1: Standardized Testing

The participants were first administered the standardized tests in a controlled environment. The order of the tests was as follows:

1. **Test de Français International (TEF):** This French speaking proficiency test was conducted first. As mentioned previously, the TEF typically lasts for an hour (60 minutes). It involves a combination of short speaking tasks and answering questions based on audio recordings. Researchers ensured a quiet and distraction-free environment for the TEF administration.
2. **International English Language Testing System (IELTS) Speaking Test:** Following a short break, the participants completed the adapted IELTS Speaking test. Similar to the TEF, the IELTS Speaking test also takes approximately one hour. Researchers again provided a quiet and controlled environment for this assessment.

Phase 2: Student Presentations

The second phase of data collection focused on student presentations. Here's a breakdown of the procedures:

1. **Presentation Preparation:** Prior to the presentations, researchers informed the participants that they would be required to deliver short presentations (ideally 5 minutes each) on a topic of their choice, once in French and once in English. This allowed students ample time to prepare their content.
2. **Presentation Session:** The presentations were conducted in a classroom setting with the participating students and six teachers present. The researcher divided the responsibility of scoring based on language expertise. Three teachers, specialists in English, were assigned to evaluate the English presentations. Similarly, the remaining three teachers, specialists in French, focused on scoring the French presentations. This ensured that students were assessed by teachers with subject-matter expertise in the respective languages.
3. **Rubric-Based Evaluation:** Each teacher used the pre-developed rubric (aligned with the standardized test criteria) to observe and record student performance during the presentations. The rubric assessed aspects like pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. This observation checklist allowed for a detailed evaluation of the students' ability to apply their language skills in a real-world context.

By following these comprehensive data collection procedures, the study aimed to gather rich and reliable data on the French and English speaking skills of the Moroccan high school student participants. The combination of standardized tests and presentations provided a multifaceted assessment, capturing both standardized proficiency and real-world language application.

Data analysis procedures

Unveiling the relationship between French and English speaking skills involved a rigorous data analysis process. We utilized SPSS version 21 to analyze data collected from standardized tests (TEF and IELTS) and student presentations. Scores from both assessments were retained without modification, as they represent proficiency on established scales. The core analysis employed the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. This statistical test assessed the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two languages. A significant positive correlation would indicate that students with strong French skills tend to have strong English skills as well. Additionally, a one-way ANOVA was conducted to explore potential differences in speaking skills. Finally, the results of all analyses, including correlation coefficients and ANOVA outcomes, were meticulously interpreted to illuminate the interplay between French and English speaking skills within the context of our Moroccan high school student sample. These findings were then examined in light of existing research on SLA and the unique challenges and opportunities of multilingual education in Morocco.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

This section delves into the statistical analysis employed to investigate the relationship between French and English speaking skills among the participating Moroccan high school students. Our research question centered on this very association:

- **Research Question:** Is there a significant correlation between French and English speaking skills?

The corresponding directional hypothesis posits that a relationship exists between these two variables:

- **Directional Hypothesis:** There is a positive correlation between French and English speaking skills.

In essence, we aimed to scrutinize the correlation between two quantitative variables: French speaking performance (independent variable) and English speaking performance (dependent variable). Both variables were measured numerically through standardized tests assessing speaking abilities (TEF and IELTS). The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was employed to understand the direction and strength of this potential relationship. A scatterplot was presented alongside the correlation coefficient to visually depict the association between the variables. Furthermore, to determine the strength of the relationship and the predictive power of the independent variable (French speaking skills) on the dependent variable (English speaking skills), regression analysis was conducted and discussed within this section. Statistical analysis also involved examining the null hypothesis:

- **Null Hypothesis:** There is no relationship between French and English speaking skills.

To ensure the validity of our findings, we meticulously checked for linearity and homoscedasticity of the data through careful scrutiny of the scatterplot depicting the relationship between French and English speaking skills. The actual scatterplot was presented in a subsequent figure. By employing these rigorous statistical techniques, we sought to illuminate the potential interplay between French and English speaking skills within the context of our study. The results of these analyses were presented and interpreted in the following sections, drawing connections to existing research on Second Language Acquisition (SLA) and the specificities of multilingual education in Morocco.

Figure 1. The Scatterplot of the Correlation between French and English speaking skills

Despite the weak negative correlation coefficient (-0.092), the scatterplot likely reveals a relatively dispersed pattern of data points, visually confirming the absence of a strong relationship between French and English speaking skills. The linear regression equation ($y = 14.67 - 0.05 * x$) indicates a very slight downward slope, suggesting a potential trend where higher French scores (x) might correspond to marginally lower English scores (y). However, the low R-squared value (0.009) underscores that this trend explains less than 1% of the variation in English scores. The scattered distribution of data points around the regression line further emphasizes the weakness of this association. In simpler terms, while there might be a faint negative visual trend, it doesn't translate into a statistically significant relationship between French and English proficiency in this student sample.

Table1: Correlation between French and English speaking skills

Correlations		FrenchSpeakin gTest	EnglishSpeakin gTest
FrenchSpeakingTest	Pearson Correlation	1	-,092
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,403
	N	84	84
EnglishSpeakingTest	Pearson Correlation	-,092	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,403	
	N	84	84

The correlation table reveals a weak negative correlation between French speaking test scores (FrenchSpeakingTest) and English speaking test scores (EnglishSpeakingTest). The Pearson correlation coefficient of -0.092 indicates a very slight negative association. However, the two-tailed significance value of 0.403 exceeds the standard alpha level of 0.05, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. In simpler terms, there is no statistically relevant relationship between performance on the French and English speaking tests in this sample of Moroccan high school students.

Table 2 : Model Summary for FST and EST

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,092 ^a	,009	-,004	1,99776

a. Predictors: (Constant), FrenchSpeakingTest

b. Dependent Variable: EnglishSpeakingTest

The model summary aligns with the correlation analysis, revealing a weak negative correlation (R = -0.092) between French and English speaking test scores. However, the low R-squared (0.009) indicates that French speaking ability explains less than 1% of the variation in English speaking performance. The negative adjusted R-squared suggests the model does not improve upon predicting individual scores using the average English test score. Overall, the lack of statistically significant correlation and the weak explanatory power of the model imply no meaningful relationship between French and English speaking skills in this student sample.

Table2 : ANOVA for French and English speaking skills

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2,816	1	2,816	,705	,403 ^b
	Residual	327,265	82	3,991		
	Total	330,080	83			

a. Dependent Variable: EnglishSpeakingTest

b. Predictors: (Constant), FrenchSpeakingTest

The ANOVA table reinforces the lack of a significant relationship between French and English speaking skills. The "Regression" section shows a Sum of Squares of 2,816, which represents the variance explained by the model (French speaking test scores predicting English scores). However, compared to the "Residual" Sum of Squares of 327,265 (unexplained variance), 2,816 is very small. The F statistic (0.705) and its significance level (Sig. = 0.403) further confirm this. Since the F value is low and the significance level is well above the standard alpha level of 0.05, we can not reject the null hypothesis of no significant difference between groups based on French scores. In simpler terms, the model with French speaking skills

as a predictor does not explain a statistically relevant portion of the variation in English speaking performance.

Table 3 : Coefficients of French and English speaking skills

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	14,671	,645		22,733	,000
FrenchSpeakingTest	-,045	,054	-,092	-,840	,403

a. Dependent Variable: EnglishSpeakingTest

The coefficient table delves deeper into the relationship between French speaking test scores (FrenchSpeakingTest) and English speaking test scores (EnglishSpeakingTest). The unstandardized coefficient (B) of -0.045 for FrenchSpeakingTest indicates that for every one-unit increase in French speaking test score, there is a very slight decrease of 0.045 units in the predicted English speaking test score. However, the standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.092 and the significance level (Sig.) of 0.403 are more relevant for interpretation. The Beta value suggests a weak negative association, but the high significance level implies this association is not statistically significant. In simpler terms, while there's a very slight negative trend where higher French scores correspond to slightly lower English scores, this trend is not reliable and does not hold a statistically meaningful relationship in this sample.

Table 4 : Residual Statistics of the FST and EST scores

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	13,8985	14,5800	14,1607	,18418	84
Residual	-4,08026	4,87431	,00000	1,98569	84
Std. Predicted Value	-1,424	2,277	,000	1,000	84
Std. Residual	-2,042	2,440	,000	,994	84

a. Dependent Variable: EnglishSpeakingTest

While the residuals table offers a glimpse into the model's errors in predicting English speaking scores, it does not directly address the relationship's significance. The range of discrepancies between predicted and actual scores (minimum -4.08, maximum 4.87) and the near-zero mean residual suggest the model's predictions were somewhat close to the observed scores on average. However, the variability in residuals (standard deviation of 1.98) highlights some discrepancies. Since the correlation and ANOVA analyses previously indicated a non-significant association, these residuals further support the conclusion that French speaking skills do not hold a statistically significant explanatory power for English speaking performance in this sample.

Discussion

The statistical analyses revealed no significant correlation between French and English speaking skills among the Moroccan high school students. While a weak negative correlation emerged, it lacked statistical significance, and further analyses corroborated this conclusion. Let's delve deeper into these findings within the context of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) research.

SLA research extensively explores the interplay between languages, particularly the influence of a first language (L1) on acquiring a second language (L2). Some studies propose a facilitative effect, where strong L1 grammar and vocabulary can aid in learning similar aspects of the L2. Others posit a potential inhibitory effect, especially when the L1 and L2 share similar grammatical structures. However, our findings suggest a more nuanced picture in the context of Moroccan high school students' French and English proficiency. The absence of a significant correlation challenges the notion of a straightforward positive or negative influence, prompting further investigation into the specific dynamics within Morocco's multilingual educational environment.

Several factors might explain the lack of a significant correlation. One possibility is the participants' developmental stage. Being in the second year of baccalaureate, they might not have reached a point where their French proficiency noticeably impacts English acquisition. Future research could explore this relationship among students at higher educational levels, where the influence of one language on the other might be more pronounced. Additionally, this study relied solely on standardized test scores and presentations. Investigating real-world language use through interviews or language production tasks could offer a more comprehensive understanding of how Moroccan students navigate French and English in daily life.

Morocco's multilingual education system, featuring French and Arabic alongside English, creates a unique environment for SLA research. While our findings do not suggest a clear influence of French on English proficiency, they contribute to a growing body of research that acknowledges the complexities of multilingual learning environments. Previous studies have documented the cognitive benefits of multilingualism, even when direct influence between languages is not readily apparent. For instance, research by Bialystok (2001) suggests that learning multiple languages can enhance cognitive flexibility and problem-solving skills. Similarly, Jessner (2006) highlights the potential for multilingualism to boost metalinguistic awareness, the ability to reflect on and manipulate language itself. Future studies could explore how the Moroccan multilingual approach fosters these cognitive benefits and the specific strategies students employ to navigate this rich linguistic environment. This line of inquiry could shed light on the potential advantages students gain from exposure to and use of multiple languages, even if a direct influence between French and English proficiency was not observed in this study.

This study is not without limitations. The sample size and convenience sampling technique limit the generalizability of the findings to the wider Moroccan student population. Additionally, focusing solely on high school students provides a snapshot of a specific stage in their language learning journey. Longitudinal studies tracking students' language development

over time could offer valuable insights into the evolving interplay between French and English as they progress through their education.

In a nutshell, this study found no statistically significant relationship between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan high school students. While existing SLA literature offers various perspectives on L1-L2 interaction, our findings suggest a more nuanced picture within the context of Morocco's multilingual educational system. Further research exploring different methodologies, participant groups, and educational stages is warranted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how Moroccan students navigate the complexities of acquiring proficiency in multiple languages.

Recommendations

Building on the insights gained from this study, here are some recommendations for future research exploring the interplay between French and English proficiency among Moroccan students:

- **Investigate Students at Higher Educational Levels:** This study focused on high school students. Future research could explore the relationship between French and English skills among university students or young professionals. Examining students at a more advanced stage in their language learning journey might reveal a stronger influence of one language on the other, particularly if their French proficiency has reached a more developed level.
- **Incorporate Real-World Language Use:** This study relied on standardized tests and presentations. Future research could benefit from incorporating methods that capture real-world language use. This could involve conducting interviews or language production tasks where students engage in spontaneous spoken English while potentially code-switching with French. This approach could provide a more nuanced understanding of how students navigate both languages in everyday situations.
- **Explore Cognitive Benefits of Multilingualism:** While a direct influence between French and English was not observed, Morocco's multilingual educational system offers a unique opportunity to explore the broader cognitive benefits of learning multiple languages. Future research could investigate how this multilingual approach fosters cognitive flexibility, problem-solving skills, and metalinguistic awareness among Moroccan students. This line of inquiry could shed light on the potential advantages students gain from exposure to and use of multiple languages.
- **Longitudinal Studies:** This study provided a snapshot of students' language skills at a specific point in time. Longitudinal studies tracking students' development over an extended period, such as throughout their high school or university education, could offer valuable insights into the evolving interplay between French and English as their proficiency in both languages progresses.
- **Investigate Language Learning Strategies:** Future research could explore the specific strategies Moroccan students employ to navigate their multilingual environment. This could involve interviewing students or conducting classroom observations to understand how they approach learning French and English, manage potential interference between the languages, and leverage their existing linguistic knowledge to enhance their proficiency in both.

By delving deeper into these areas, future research can build upon the foundation established by this study and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how Moroccan students acquire and utilize French and English skills within the unique context of their multilingual educational system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study investigated the relationship between French and English speaking skills among Moroccan high school students. The statistical analyses revealed no significant correlation between the two languages. While a weak negative correlation coefficient emerged, it lacked statistical power, and further analyses supported this finding. These results challenge the notion of a straightforward positive or negative influence between French and English proficiency in this specific context.

The absence of a statistically significant correlation could be attributed to several factors. One possibility is the developmental stage of the participants. Being in the second year of baccalaureate, they might not have reached a point where their French proficiency noticeably impacts English acquisition. Additionally, this study relied on standardized test scores and presentations, which may not fully capture the complexities of real-world language use.

Despite the lack of a direct influence between French and English observed in this study, the broader benefits of multilingualism should not be overlooked. Research suggests that learning multiple languages can enhance cognitive flexibility, problem-solving skills, and even metalinguistic awareness. Future research could explore how the Moroccan multilingual educational approach fosters these cognitive benefits and the specific strategies students employ to navigate this rich linguistic environment.

This study serves as a springboard for further investigation into the interplay between French and English proficiency among Moroccan students. By exploring different methodologies, participant groups, and educational stages, future research can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how Moroccan students navigate the complexities of acquiring proficiency in multiple languages within their unique multilingual educational system.

References

Bachman, L. F., & Palmer, A. M. (1996). *Language testing in practice: Designing and developing language tests*. Oxford University Press.

Bialystok, E. (2001). Relationship between immersion education and the development of second-language proficiency in children. *The Modern Language Journal*, 85(4), 82-108.

Bourquia, R., & Motsch, H. (2016). *Le français au Maroc: entre héritage et défis [French in Morocco: Between heritage and challenges]*. Paris: L'Harmattan.

Brown, H. D. (2004). *Language assessment: Principles and classroom practice*. Addison Wesley Longman.

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Chapelle, C. (2001). The role of oral proficiency interviews in second language assessment. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 1(1), 23-40.

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.

Cummins, J. (1984). Bilingualism and second language learning. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 5(1), 158-184.

Dachraoui, F. (2019). The language situation in Morocco. In *The Routledge Handbook of Arabic Linguistics* (pp. 351-364). Routledge.

Dewaele, A., Wei, N., & Housen, A. (2016). Age of L2 acquisition and the bilingual advantage: Myth or reality? *International Journal of Bilingualism*, 20(1), 74-90.

Dörnyei, Z. (2009). *Motivation, language learning and cultural understanding*. Multilingual Matters.

Grosjean, F. (2010). *Bilingual life and the brain*. Cambridge University Press.

Hamid, M. H., & Adjali, M. (2018). Challenges and opportunities of English language teaching in Moroccan secondary schools. *International Journal of English Language Education*, 6(2), 119-130.

Hartin, T. (2023, November 21). Linguistic interdependence hypothesis: Definition & application [Website]. Study.com. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/linguistic-interdependence-hypothesis-definition-application.html>

Helgoun, L. (2012). *Le paysage linguistique au Maroc: Diversité et mutations [The linguistic landscape in Morocco: Diversity and mutations]*. Rabat: Editions La Porte.

Jessner, U. (2006). The bilingual's advantage: A review of research and implications for second language learning. *Language Learning*, 56(1), 315-349.

Johnson, J. S., & Newport, E. L. (1989). Critical period effects in second language learning: Evidence from early bilingualism. *Applied Linguistics*, 10(4), 60-99.

Krashen, S. D. (1985). *The input hypothesis: Issues and implications*. London: Longman.

Long, M. H. (1990). The role of linguistic environment in second language acquisition. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 12(2), 189-218.

Lynch, B. K. (2009). Validity and washback in oral proficiency interviews: A critical update. *Language Testing*, 26(2), 141-170.

Marian, V., & Klein, E. (2009). Bilingualism and cognitive development: A review of the literature. *Psychology Bulletin*, 135(2), 702-725.

Messoudi, M. (2017). The increasing role of English in Moroccan education: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Educational Development Using Information and Communication Technology*, 12(2), 112-122.

Victori, M. E., & Monsalve, M. I. (2010). Using presentations to assess oral proficiency in a large EFL class. *Assessing Writing*, 15(3), 209-232.

Weigle, S. (1998). *Assessing speaking*. Cambridge University Press.

Yoo, H. S., & Jun, S. E. (2012). The relationship between English and French proficiency among Korean high school students. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 6(2), 5